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Characterizing the radiation-induced defect behavior in Inconel 617 through molecular dynamics simulations

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ABSTRACT

Inconel 617, a nickel–chromium–cobalt–molybdenum superalloy, is a promising candidate for high-temperature nuclear applications due to its mechanical strength and oxidation resistance. Understanding its radiation response is crucial for evaluating its long-term performance. In this study, we employed molecular dynamics (MD) simulations with a modified embedded atom method (MEAM) potential to investigate defect formation and evolution in Inconel 617 with the composition $\text{Ni}_{52}\text{Cr}_{23.5}\text{Co}_{11.4}\text{Mo}_{9.7}\text{Fe}_{1.6}\text{Al}_{1.8}$, under single-cascade and successive overlapping cascade simulations up to 0.2 displacements per atom (dpa). Successive cascade simulations revealed that Inconel 617 exhibits a defect concentration comparable to values reported in the literature for equimolar NiCrCo. However, it forms fewer dislocations and smaller defect clusters, suggesting improved radiation resistance up to 0.2 dpa. To isolate the role of molybdenum (Mo), we also examined a comparable alloy ($\text{Ni}_{59.8}\text{Cr}_{27.1}\text{Co}_{13.1}$) without Mo. Our results show that, while Mo does not significantly affect the number of Frenkel pairs (FPs) produced in single 5 keV cascades, it suppresses the formation of large interstitial clusters during successive cascade overlap simulations, thereby enhancing radiation resistance. Tensile simulations indicate that irradiation-induced dislocations reduce both the yield strength and Young's modulus. These findings provide insights into the radiation tolerance of Inconel 617 and highlight the critical role of Mo in defect dynamics.

1. Introduction

High-performance structural materials are crucial for advanced energy systems, where extreme conditions such as high temperatures, intense radiation, and corrosive environments impose significant demands on material performance. Among the candidate materials for such applications, Inconel 617, a nickel–chromium–cobalt–molybdenum superalloy, has gained considerable attention due to its exceptional mechanical strength at high temperatures [1–4], thermal stability [5], creep resistance [6–8], and hot corrosion resistance [9,10]. Consequently, Inconel 617 has been widely utilized for decades in diverse industrial sectors, including aviation, gas turbines, pressure vessels, and metallurgical processing facilities. Its microstructure, primarily composed of a face-centered cubic (fcc) γ phase, ensures excellent high-temperature performance, while the ordered γ' phase (L1₂

structure), which develops after prolonged annealing, further enhances its strength [8,11].

Due to its superior high-temperature properties, Inconel 617 was formally included in the ASME Boiler and Pressure Vessel Code (Section III, Division 5) in 2019 by the American Society of Mechanical Engineers—the first metallic material to be added in three decades—confirming its suitability for Generation IV high-temperature nuclear reactor. One of the most demanding applications for this alloy is in the Intermediate Heat Exchanger (IHX), where it must withstand temperatures approaching 950 °C, pressures up to 7 MPa, and a highly radioactive environment for up to 60 years [8,12]. Given these extreme conditions, understanding the radiation response of Inconel 617 is crucial for ensuring its long-term structural integrity in nuclear applications.

Several previous experimental studies by other researchers have

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Table 1

Comparison of the shear modulus (G) and Poisson's ratio (ν) of Inconel 617 at $T = 25^\circ\text{C}$ between experimental results [43] and values obtained using the MEAM interatomic potential. Our calculations were performed for $\text{Ni}_{54.1}\text{Cr}_{22.6}\text{Co}_{11.6}\text{Mo}_{8.6}\text{Fe}_{1.7}\text{Al}_{1.4}$, excluding elements below 0.5 atomic percent from the chemical composition of Inconel 617 in Ref. [43].

	G (GPa)	ν
Experiment [43]	78.1	0.303
MD (current 2NN MEAM)	85.99	0.315

Table 2

The average number of FPs at the end of a 5 keV single cascade in Inconel 617-S and $\text{Ni}_{59.8}\text{Cr}_{27.1}\text{Co}_{13.1}$.

	Inconel 617-S	$\text{Ni}_{59.8}\text{Cr}_{27.1}\text{Co}_{13.1}$
N_{FPs}	11.25 ± 3.28	9.89 ± 3.08

due to the formation of extended defects, such as dislocation loops and He bubbles, induced by irradiation. In particular, works by [13–18] have reported defect accumulation, microstructural evolution, and mechanical property degradation in irradiated Inconel 617 under various irradiation conditions. However, despite these experimental efforts, fundamental studies on radiation damage accumulation in Inconel 617 and the influence of its chemical composition remain limited.

To address this gap, we investigate a simplified model of Inconel 617, referred to as Inconel 617-S. This model ($\text{Ni}_{52}\text{Cr}_{23.5}\text{Co}_{11.4}\text{Mo}_{9.7}\text{Fe}_{1.6}\text{Al}_{1.8}$) includes the primary elements of Inconel 617 but omits minor alloying elements. To better understand the radiation resistance of Inconel 617-S and to explore the role of its constituent elements, we isolate the effect of molybdenum (Mo), a significant alloying element in Inconel 617-S that is not typically present in equimolar NiCrCo-based medium-entropy alloys (MEAs). Previous studies have demonstrated that equimolar NiCrCo MEAs—typically designed without Mo—possess favorable radiation resistance characteristics [19–23]. By comparing the radiation response of 617-S with a Mo-free analog ($\text{Ni}_{59.8}\text{Cr}_{27.1}\text{Co}_{13.1}$) that has comparable Ni/Co, Ni/Cr, and Co/Cr ratios, we aim to evaluate whether Mo contributes positively or negatively to radiation tolerance. While alloy design is not the primary objective of this study, insights into the role of Mo may support future efforts to optimize radiation-resistant NiCoCr-based alloys for nuclear applications.

Additionally, to evaluate the impact of radiation damage on mechanical performance, we conduct uniaxial tensile tests on irradiated Inconel 617-S and $\text{Ni}_{59.8}\text{Cr}_{27.1}\text{Co}_{13.1}$ using MD simulations. This combined approach offers a comprehensive understanding of radiation-induced defect dynamics and their mechanical implications.

Fig. 1. Workflow for molecular dynamics simulations of overlapping cascades used to model radiation damage accumulation up to a specified dose. Only the PKA atom and the simulation boxes are shown; atoms within the boxes are not displayed.

investigated the irradiation behavior of Inconel 617, focusing on neutron, xenon, and helium ion irradiation [13–18]. These studies reveal that radiation-induced hardening and dislocation pinning occur

Fig. 2. Evolution of Frenkel pairs as a function of time during a single cascade in Inconel 617-S. Vacancies are shown in blue, and interstitials in red.

Fig. 3. (a) Defect concentration and (b) Dislocation density as a function of cascade number (dose) in Inconel 617-S and $\text{Ni}_{59.8}\text{Cr}_{27.1}\text{Co}_{13.1}$ for the [001] cell. Snapshots of interstitials, vacancies, and dislocations at ~ 0.2 dpa in (c) Inconel 617-S and (d) $\text{Ni}_{59.8}\text{Cr}_{27.1}\text{Co}_{13.1}$.

2. Simulation method

This study employs molecular dynamics simulations to investigate displacement damage and mechanical degradation in Inconel 617-S and $\text{Ni}_{59.8}\text{Cr}_{27.1}\text{Co}_{13.1}$ under irradiation. Displacement damage is a key mechanism affecting metallic alloys exposed to neutron irradiation, where a neutron transfers sufficient energy to an atom, ejecting it from its lattice site and generating a primary knock-on atom (PKA). The PKA initiates a collision cascade, leading to a localized thermal spike, which dissipates within a few picoseconds, leaving behind residual defects such as vacancies and interstitials. Due to its ability to capture ultrafast defect dynamics, MD simulations provide an effective tool for modeling the primary stages of radiation damage. This approach has been widely used to estimate early-stage damage in metals and alloys [24–29]. While single-cascade simulations provide insight into initial defect formation, successive overlapping cascades are necessary to capture defect accumulation as a function of dose [20,25,30–32].

All simulations were performed using the Large-scale Atomic/Molecular Massively Parallel Simulator (LAMMPS) [33]. The second nearest-neighbor modified embedded atom method (2NN MEAM) potential has been extensively used to study Ni-Co-based multi-principal element alloys (MPEAs) under deformation and irradiation, and has often yielded results consistent with experimental findings [24,29,34–36]. In this study, we employed the 2NN MEAM potential developed by Wang et al. [37] to describe the interactions between Mo-Co-Ni-Fe-Al-Cr atoms. This potential has recently been applied to Ni-based superalloys under deformation, showing good agreement with microstructural evolution observed in experimental TEM studies [38]. To accurately capture short-range atomic interactions resulting from high-energy cascades, all pairwise interactions were smoothly connected to the ZBL universal repulsive potential [39] (see Supplementary Section S1 and Figure S1 for further details). To ensure the reliability of

this interatomic potential, we validated its accuracy by comparing the predicted elastic properties with available experimental data for Inconel 617 (see Table 1). For this purpose, we used a reference composition of $\text{Ni}_{54.1}\text{Cr}_{22.6}\text{Co}_{11.6}\text{Mo}_{8.6}\text{Fe}_{1.7}\text{Al}_{1.4}$, as reported in Ref. [40], excluding elements present at concentrations below 0.5 atomic percent. This composition was selected because Ref. [40] provides experimental values for mechanical properties, enabling us to assess the accuracy of the potential under experimentally relevant conditions. It should be noted that this composition is slightly different from that of Inconel 617-S. The elastic constants were computed using a fast deformation–fluctuation hybrid approach [41], while the effective isotropic elastic constants, derived using Liebfried’s method, were used to determine the elastic modulus and Poisson’s ratio [42]. The results show good agreement between the MEAM potential and experimental data for both elastic modulus and Poisson’s ratio.

To investigate radiation-induced defect production and accumulation, we performed single cascade and overlapping cascade simulations in Inconel 617-S and $\text{Ni}_{59.8}\text{Cr}_{27.1}\text{Co}_{13.1}$ alloys. The simulations were conducted in two face-centered cubic (FCC) supercells with different crystallographic orientations. The first simulation cell consisted of a $32 \times 32 \times 32$ conventional FCC supercell containing 131,072 Ni atoms, oriented along $X = [100]$, $Y = [010]$, and $Z = [001]$, referred to as the [001] cell. The second simulation cell had a $45 \times 30 \times 20$ conventional FCC supercell containing 162,000 Ni atoms, oriented along $X = [\bar{1}01]$, $Y = [1\bar{2}1]$, and $Z = [111]$, referred to as the [111] cell. In both cases, random substitution of Ni atoms with Co, Cr, Mo, Al, and Fe was performed to achieve the desired composition ($\text{Ni}_{52}\text{Cr}_{23.5}\text{Co}_{11.4}\text{Mo}_{9.7}\text{Fe}_{1.6}\text{Al}_{1.8}$ for the Inconel 617-S alloy and $\text{Ni}_{59.8}\text{Cr}_{27.1}\text{Co}_{13.1}$ for the Mo-free alloy). Periodic boundary conditions (PBCs) were imposed in all three directions. The system was first energy-minimized using the conjugate gradient method, followed by equilibration at 300 K and zero

Fig. 4. (a) Defect concentration and (b) Dislocation density as a function of cascade number (dose) in Inconel 617-S and $\text{Ni}_{59.8}\text{Cr}_{27.1}\text{Co}_{13.1}$ for the [111] cell. Snapshots of interstitials, vacancies, and dislocations at ~ 0.2 dpa in (c) Inconel 617-S and (d) $\text{Ni}_{59.8}\text{Cr}_{27.1}\text{Co}_{13.1}$.

pressure using the NPT ensemble for 100 ps.

To simulate irradiation events, we followed the procedure outlined in Fig. 1. A central atom was assigned a recoil energy of 5 keV in a random direction, initiating a collision cascade. To accurately resolve the fast atomic dynamics in the early ballistic phase, we employed a variable timestep scheme: 0.05 fs for the first 2 ps, 0.1 fs for the next 2 ps, and 1 fs for the final 16 ps of the simulation. To prevent excessive heating, the outer 4 Å regions of the simulation box were thermostatted at 300 K using a Berendsen thermostat [43]. Subsequently, in the second step, the entire system was maintained at 300 K for another 20 ps, with pressure controlled using a Berendsen barostat [43]. For primary radiation damage analysis, we conducted 100 independent single-cascade simulations (with varying PKA directions and atom types) following steps 1 and 2 in Fig. 1 to compare defect formation in Inconel 617-S and $\text{Ni}_{59.8}\text{Cr}_{27.1}\text{Co}_{13.1}$ alloys. To investigate defect accumulation over time, we performed overlapping cascade simulations, in which, after completing steps 1 and 2, all atoms were randomly shifted across periodic boundaries to simulate a homogeneous irradiation effect (Step 3). This process was repeated hundreds of times to achieve an accumulated dose of ~ 0.2 displacements per atom (dpa), calculated using the NRT-dpa approximation [44]:

$$\frac{N_d}{N} = \frac{0.8 T_d}{2E_d N} N_{\text{cascade}} \quad (1)$$

Where N_{cascade} is the number of cascades, N represents the total number of atoms in the simulation box, N_d is the NRT-predicted atomic displacements for the damage energy T_d . In this formula, E_d is the displacement threshold energy. We calculated E_d for each alloy using the 2NN MEAM interatomic. Specifically, we performed a statistically

robust evaluation of the minimum energy required to permanently displace an atom from its lattice site using MD simulations. The full methodology and supporting diagrams are provided in Supplementary Section S2. Our results show that E_d is 48.4 ± 0.1 eV for Inconel 617-S, and 48.2 ± 0.1 eV for $\text{Ni}_{59.8}\text{Cr}_{27.1}\text{Co}_{13.1}$.

To investigate the effect of irradiation on mechanical properties, we performed uniaxial tensile tests using molecular dynamics simulations at various irradiation doses. The tests were conducted along two distinct crystallographic directions to capture orientation-dependent mechanical responses: the [010] direction for the [001] cell and the [111] direction for the [111] cell. The [010] and [111] orientations were chosen because they represent two fundamentally different high-symmetry directions in FCC crystals with distinct atomic arrangements and packing densities. Loading along [010] aligns with a principal cubic axis offering geometric simplicity, while loading along [111] follows the close-packed atomic direction characterized by higher atomic density [45]. These differences influence stress distribution and defect behavior under tensile loading. During deformation, the NPT ensemble was used to maintain zero pressure in the directions perpendicular to the loading axis, while strain-controlled loading was applied along the loading direction. PBCs were applied in all directions. Simulations were conducted at 300 K with a constant strain rate $\dot{\epsilon} = 2 \times 10^8$ 1/s.

To analyze the concentration of vacancies and interstitials, the Wigner-Seitz cell method [11] was employed. To determine the distribution of vacancy and interstitial clusters, a cluster analysis was performed using a cutoff distance defined as the mean of the second and third nearest neighbors of the atoms. The Dislocation Extraction Algorithm (DXA) [13] was used to track dislocation evolution during both cascade simulations and tensile tests. It should be noted that the DXA

Fig. 5. Distribution of interstitial clusters in (a) Inconel 617-S and (b) $\text{Ni}_{59.8}\text{Cr}_{27.1}\text{Co}_{13.1}$, and distribution of vacancy clusters in (c) Inconel 617-S and (d) $\text{Ni}_{59.8}\text{Cr}_{27.1}\text{Co}_{13.1}$, across various cluster sizes. All data correspond to the [001] simulation cell.

identifies dislocations based purely on the local crystal structure and does not consider atomic species. In concentrated alloys, however, chemical disorder can introduce local lattice distortions that may affect structural analysis. To ensure that DXA is applicable to the multi-principal element alloys investigated in this study, we employed Common Neighbor Analysis (CNA) alongside DXA. CNA was used to confirm that the local FCC crystal structure was preserved despite the chemical complexity. OVITO software was used to analyze and visualize the results [46].

3. Results

3.1. Single cascade

The evolution of Frenkel pairs (FPs) during a collision cascade initiated by a 5 keV PKA at 300 K in Inconel 617-S is shown in Fig. 2. The number of FPs increases sharply at the beginning of the cascade, reaching its maximum at the end of the ballistically induced displacement phase, also known as the thermal spike, within 1 ps. Subsequently, FPs undergo recombination, leaving behind a small number of surviving vacancies and interstitials. To ensure statistical reliability, we performed 100 single-cascade simulations for each alloy. Table 2 reports the average number of surviving FPs at the end of the 5 keV cascades for Inconel 617-S and $\text{Ni}_{59.8}\text{Cr}_{27.1}\text{Co}_{13.1}$. While the values differ slightly, the variations fall within the statistical uncertainty, and no definitive conclusion can be drawn regarding a significant difference in defect production between the two alloys.

3.2. Defect accumulation

While single-cascade simulations provide fundamental insights into defect formation in the primary damage state, they do not fully capture

the radiation response of these alloys. To investigate defect accumulation and its dependence on irradiation dose, we conducted extensive overlapping cascade simulations in two simulation cells for each alloy. Figs. 3 and 4 depict defect evolution as a function of cascade number (dose) for the [001] and [111] cells.

Figs. 3a and 4a compare the evolution of radiation-induced defects in Inconel 617-S and $\text{Ni}_{59.8}\text{Cr}_{27.1}\text{Co}_{13.1}$ across different simulation cell orientations. At lower doses, both alloys show similar defect percentages. However, as dose increases, $\text{Ni}_{59.8}\text{Cr}_{27.1}\text{Co}_{13.1}$ accumulates more defects, while Inconel 617-S shows signs of saturation. This divergence is clearer and occurs earlier in the [111] simulation cell, likely due to its larger size. Figs. 3c-d and 4c-d present atomic configurations at 0.2 dpa, highlighting notable differences in defect morphology between the two alloys. Inconel 617-S shows no evidence of Frank loops in either simulation cell, while $\text{Ni}_{59.8}\text{Cr}_{27.1}\text{Co}_{13.1}$ clearly forms large sessile Frank loops composed of interstitial clusters. Both alloys, however, exhibit similar types of common radiation-induced defects, including isolated interstitials and vacancies, small clusters, glissile dislocation chains primarily composed of Shockley partials, and stair-rod dislocations associated with trapped vacancy clusters. The results in Figs. 3b and 4b indicate that dislocation density increases more rapidly in $\text{Ni}_{59.8}\text{Cr}_{27.1}\text{Co}_{13.1}$ than in Inconel 617-S, particularly after the early stages of irradiation. We also analyzed interstitial and vacancy clusters at various doses, with the results shown in Figs. 5 and 6. Figs. 5a, 5b, 6a, and 6b indicate that $\text{Ni}_{59.8}\text{Cr}_{27.1}\text{Co}_{13.1}$ contains more interstitials in larger clusters compared to Inconel 617-S, particularly at higher irradiation doses. In contrast, no significant difference is observed in the vacancy cluster size distributions between the two alloys (Figs. 5c, 5d, 6c, and 6d), although the number of isolated vacancies in $\text{Ni}_{59.8}\text{Cr}_{27.1}\text{Co}_{13.1}$ is higher than in Inconel 617-S. The difference in cluster behavior between the two alloys is more pronounced in the [111] cell, likely due to its larger simulation volume compared to the [001]

Fig. 6. Distribution of interstitial clusters in (a) Inconel 617-S and (b) Ni_{59.8}Cr_{27.1}Co_{13.1}, and distribution of vacancy clusters in (c) Inconel 617-S and (d) Ni_{59.8}Cr_{27.1}Co_{13.1}, across various cluster sizes. All data correspond to the [111] simulation cell.

cell. The reduced formation of large interstitial clusters in Inconel 617-S may be associated with compositional effects, potentially influenced by the presence of 9.7 at. % Mo.

3.3. Effect of low dose radiation damage on tensile properties

Uniaxial tensile tests were performed on Inconel 617-S and Ni_{59.8}Cr_{27.1}Co_{13.1} single crystals at various irradiation doses. The results for the [001] cell are shown in Fig. 7, while those for the [111] cell are presented in Fig. 8. The stress-strain curves in Figs. 7a, 7c, 8a, and 8c highlight the significant impact of irradiation-induced defects on the mechanical properties of both alloys. In both cases, irradiation leads to a decrease in yield strength (YS) (Figs. 7b, 7d, 8b, and 8d), with Ni_{59.8}Cr_{27.1}Co_{13.1} exhibiting a greater reduction in YS compared to Inconel 617-S.

For the [001] cell, YS correlates strongly with the dislocation density induced by irradiation, following the general trend that higher dislocation densities lead to lower YS during tensile deformation. However, no clear correlation between YS and radiation dose was observed up to 0.2 dpa (Figs. 7b and 7d). In contrast, for the [111] cell, YS shows a direct correlation with dose (number of cascades), where an increase in dose leads to a continuous decrease in YS (Figs. 8b and 8d).

To investigate the effect of irradiation on Young's modulus, we performed linear regression fits within the initial elastic regime of the stress-strain curves. Specifically, we used a strain range of 0.001–0.005 for the [001] orientation and 0.0005–0.0025 for the [111] orientation, where the mechanical response remains linear and elastic. As shown in Fig. 9, Young's modulus exhibits a general decreasing trend with increasing initial dislocation density, which was induced by irradiation, in both alloys and crystallographic directions. The observed reduction in Young's modulus is modest, typically on the order of 3–5 %, which is consistent with the early-stage softening effects caused by irradiation-

induced dislocation networks.

To identify the active slip planes during deformation, we analyzed the atomic shear strain fields using OVITO. In the unirradiated cells, we confirmed activation of the {111} slip planes, which is consistent with the well-established deformation behavior of FCC crystals. Slip plane activation patterns varied with loading direction. In the [001] cell (loaded along [010]), all four {111} slip planes, including (111), were active. In contrast, the [111] cell (loaded along [111]) exhibited slip on the ($\bar{1}11$), ($1\bar{1}1$), and ($11\bar{1}$) planes, while activity on the (111) plane was not observed. Fig. 10 presents snapshots of shear strain localization for unirradiated and irradiated Inconel 617-S samples (after 155 successive cascades), representing high dislocation density in the [001] cell. At the onset of plastic deformation, slip initiates on the ($11\bar{1}$) and (111) planes in both cases. As strain increases, activation extends to all four {111} planes. At a strain level of $\epsilon = 0.13$, both samples reach comparable stress levels, providing a consistent basis for comparison. While the same slip systems appear to be activated, the irradiated sample shows a tendency toward more fragmented and discontinuous slip planes (see some quantitative analysis in Supplementary section S3), possibly influenced by irradiation-induced defects.

4. Discussion

Fig. 2 shows that the employed interatomic potential can properly simulate primary radiation damage by reproducing all stages of radiation damage, including the ballistic phase, thermal spike, and defect recombination processes. While Table 2 shows slight differences in the average number of surviving Frenkel pairs between Inconel 617-S and Ni_{59.8}Cr_{27.1}Co_{13.1}, these differences fall within the statistical uncertainty. Therefore, no definitive conclusion can be drawn regarding the impact of alloy composition on defect production in 5 keV single-

Fig. 7. (a, c) Stress-strain curves from tensile tests on Inconel 617-S and Ni_{59.8}Cr_{27.1}Co_{13.1} at 300 K, before and after irradiation at various doses (successive cascade numbers). (b, d) Yield strength (YS) vs. initial dislocation density induced by irradiation in both alloys. The top x-axis shows the corresponding cascade numbers for the induced dislocations. All results correspond to the [001] cell.

cascade simulations.

Levo et al. [20] studied radiation damage in Ni, NiCo, NiFe, NiCrCo, and NiFeCo at room temperature using an EAM interatomic potential. Their findings showed that NiCrCo exhibited the lowest defect concentration among all compositions [20]. To compare our results with that study, Figs. 3a and 4a show that at 0.2 dpa, the defect concentration in Inconel 617-S (0.004) is comparable to that of equimolar NiCrCo (~0.004 at 0.2 dpa) in a simulation cell of the same size. By comparing the findings of that study with our results, it appears that although the point defect concentration is similar, equimolar NiCrCo exhibits a higher number of dislocations and larger dislocation structures than Inconel 617-S under irradiation up to 0.2 dpa. These findings indicate that Inconel 617-S has enhanced radiation resistance relative to equimolar NiCrCo medium entropy alloy.

The results in Figs. 3–6 show that Inconel 617-S exhibits lower defect accumulation than Ni_{59.8}Cr_{27.1}Co_{13.1} at higher doses. This trend points to compositional effects that influence long-term defect evolution, with Mo being a possible contributing factor. Figs. 3–6 demonstrate that Inconel 617-S exhibits a lower dislocation density and smaller interstitial clusters compared to Ni_{59.8}Cr_{27.1}Co_{13.1}. A possible explanation for this effect is the low mobility of Mo as an interstitial, which can be attributed to its high atomic mass. Molybdenum (95.95 u) is approximately 1.63 times heavier than nickel (58.69 u) and cobalt (58.93 u), and 1.85 times heavier than chromium (51.99 u). The increased mass of Mo reduces its diffusivity as an interstitial, thereby limiting the mobility of small interstitial clusters and inhibiting their coalescence into larger

defects. To confirm that Mo interstitials contribute to this behavior, we analyzed the distribution of different atomic species in interstitials and compared it to their concentrations in the bulk matrix (Fig. 11).

The results show small fluctuations in the atomic composition of interstitials compared to their overall matrix concentration in Inconel 617-S. Since PKAs were randomly selected at the center of the simulation box, some fluctuations in PKA composition are expected. However, as the dose increases, the variation in PKA composition (relative to matrix concentration) becomes less significant compared to the fluctuations in interstitial composition (Figs. 11b and 11d). Apart from these minor fluctuations, Mo is present in interstitials at a concentration close to its overall proportion in Inconel 617-S. Therefore, we conclude that the limited formation of large interstitial clusters in Inconel 617-S is likely related to the reduced mobility of small interstitials. This behavior may be influenced by alloy composition, with Mo potentially playing a role in slowing interstitial diffusion.

Frank interstitial loops typically form when interstitial clusters grow beyond a critical size. In Inconel 617-S, the formation of such loops appears to be suppressed, likely due to the reduced mobility of small interstitial clusters. In contrast, large sessile Frank loops are observed in Ni_{59.8}Cr_{27.1}Co_{13.1} (see Figs 3c-d and 4c-d), indicating that interstitial clusters are more mobile and prone to coalescence in this alloy. This difference in defect evolution helps explain why Inconel 617-S exhibits near-saturation behavior in defect accumulation, while Ni_{59.8}Cr_{27.1}Co_{13.1} continues to accumulate defects with increasing dose. Once formed, Frank loops are energetically stable and exhibit low

Fig. 8. (a, c) Stress-strain curves from tensile tests on Inconel 617-S and Ni_{59.8}Cr_{27.1}Co_{13.1} at 300 K, before and after irradiation at various doses (successive cascade numbers). (b, d) Yield strength (YS) as a function of successive cascade numbers prior to tensile testing. The top x-axis shows the corresponding initial dislocation density induced by irradiation. All results correspond to the [111] cell.

mobility, which limits their ability to recombine with vacancies. At 300 K, vacancy diffusion is significantly slower than interstitial diffusion, further reducing the likelihood of recombination between sessile loops and vacancies. In contrast, smaller interstitial clusters, such as those more commonly formed in Inconel 617-S, remain mobile and are more likely to recombine with vacancies, thereby limiting long-term defect growth.

We performed tensile tests at various irradiation doses in Inconel 617-S and Ni_{59.8}Cr_{27.1}Co_{13.1}, with the results presented in Figs. 7 and 8. The yield stress observed in our MD simulations is notably higher compared to typical experimental values. This discrepancy arises primarily due to inherent methodological limitations in MD simulations. Specifically, the nanoscale dimensions of the simulation cells significantly constrain the available volume for dislocation nucleation, multiplication, and mobility, thus artificially elevating the measured yield stress. This size-dependent strengthening behavior, attributed to finite-volume constraints on dislocation processes, has been previously discussed in the context of micropillar experiments [47]. Furthermore, since deformation in MD simulations occurs over extremely short time scales (on the order of nanoseconds), the resulting strain rates are substantially higher than those achievable experimentally. Such elevated strain rates restrict the time available for thermally activated dislocation nucleation, further amplifying the yield stress values above experimental observations [48].

While multiple MD simulations on FCC alloys have reported a decrease in yield strength with an increase in point defects [32,49],

these studies primarily focused on isolated point defect effects. In contrast, our study investigates the influence of extended defects, specifically irradiation-induced dislocations, which form during 650 (815) successive cascade simulations in the [001] ([111]) cells, on the material's tensile behavior. We observed a strong correlation between irradiation-induced defects and yield strength. When irradiation occurs in the [001] cell with loading along [010], dislocations induced by irradiation play a dominant role in yield strength reduction in both alloys. However, when irradiation occurs in the [111] cell with loading along [111], not only dislocations but also other defects, including defect clusters, contribute to yield strength reduction, where YS decreases as dose increases.

Experimental studies on FCC metals and alloys have provided evidence of radiation hardening at low and medium doses through tensile testing of irradiated crystals [50–52]. In these cases, radiation hardening is typically attributed to the initial locking of dislocation by irradiation-induced defects. However, in MD simulations, the absence of pre-existing dislocation lines prevents dislocation pinning, which is commonly observed in experiments. Additionally, MD simulations operate on shorter time scales and higher strain rates, making it difficult to fully capture the slower defect dynamics observed in experiments.

Our MD simulations indicate that irradiation-induced defects, particularly dislocations, play a crucial role in plastic deformation. Fig. 12a shows that the dislocation density in the irradiated sample of Inconel 617-S increases at lower strain levels compared to the non-irradiated sample, suggesting premature yielding due to irradiation-

Fig. 9. Young's modulus as a function of initial dislocation density induced by irradiation prior to tensile testing: (a) Inconel 617-S with loading along [010], (b) $\text{Ni}_{59.8}\text{Cr}_{27.1}\text{Co}_{13.1}$ with loading along [010], (c) Inconel 617-S with loading along [111], and (d) $\text{Ni}_{59.8}\text{Cr}_{27.1}\text{Co}_{13.1}$ with loading along [111].

induced defects. Figs. 12b and 12c illustrate dislocation evolution during tensile deformation along [010]. In the non-irradiated sample (Fig. 12b), dislocations form only after higher strain levels ($\sim 8.0\%$). In contrast, in the irradiated sample (Fig. 12c), pre-existing irradiation-induced dislocations are already present at $\varepsilon = 0\%$ and continue to grow as strain increases. This suggests that irradiation-induced dislocations reduce the stress required for plastic deformation, leading to earlier yielding in the irradiated sample. The correlation between yield strength (YS) and radiation dose up to 0.2 dpa can be attributed to the increase in dislocation density and defect clusters induced by irradiation. One possible explanation is the loading direction effect. When the loading direction is [111], dislocation nucleation from small defect clusters is more favorable than in [010] loading, increasing the contribution of non-dislocation defects to yield strength reduction.

Additionally, to evaluate the impact of irradiation on elastic properties, we analyzed changes in Young's modulus in both alloys and crystallographic directions. As shown in Fig. 9, defect accumulation, particularly increased dislocation density, leads to a measurable reduction in stiffness. It should be noted that some fluctuations in the modulus reduction may arise from the complex nature of defect networks, where factors beyond total dislocation density, such as defect type, distribution, and interactions, also influence the material's elastic response. A similar explanation may explain the fluctuations in yield

strength as a function of the initial dislocation density induced by irradiation, as observed in Fig. 7.

To verify the accuracy of the Young's modulus values obtained from stress-strain analysis, we compared them with theoretical estimates derived from the elastic constants of the unirradiated samples [53]:

$$E_{[001]} = \frac{(C_{11} - C_{12})(C_{11} + 2C_{12})}{(C_{11} + C_{12})}$$

Table 3 summarizes the calculated C_{11} and C_{12} values, the theoretical Young's modulus using established elasticity relations, and the modulus obtained via linear regression of the stress-strain curves. The strong agreement between theory and simulation supports the consistency of our approach and the reliability of the extracted mechanical properties.

Furthermore, the observed softening in Young's modulus under irradiation is consistent with theoretical models of dislocation networks, which demonstrate that increasing dislocation density introduces an anelastic component to the material's response, thereby reducing the apparent stiffness of the crystal [54].

Our results show that irradiation does not alter the set of active slip systems in FCC Inconel 617-S but does influence the morphology and continuity of the resulting shear bands. In both unirradiated and irradiated samples, plastic deformation initiates on the energetically favorable $\{111\}$ slip planes. However, irradiation-induced defects

Fig. 10. Snapshots of shear strain localization in Inconel 617-S during loading along the [010] direction in the [001] cell: (a) unirradiated sample and (b) irradiated sample after 155 successive cascades.

disrupt the spatial coherence of dislocation activity, resulting in more fragmented and heterogeneous strain localization in the irradiated material.

This observation aligns with the established understanding of FCC plasticity, where dislocation glide predominantly occurs on $\{111\}$ planes along $\langle 110 \rangle$ directions due to their high atomic packing density and low critical resolved shear stress (CRSS) [45,55]. However, we note that due to the inherent limitations of molecular dynamics such as the small simulation cell size, high strain rates, and the relatively modest irradiation doses further differentiation of irradiation effects on specific shear planes remains challenging. Future work should address these constraints to more precisely resolve the interaction between irradiation-induced defects and slip system activation.

5. Conclusion

In this study, we employed molecular dynamics (MD) simulations with a modified embedded atom method (MEAM) potential to investigate radiation-induced defect formation and accumulation in Inconel 617-S and $\text{Ni}_{59.8}\text{Cr}_{27.1}\text{Co}_{13.1}$ under single-cascade and overlapping cascade simulations up to 0.2 dpa. Our key findings are:

1. While no significant difference was observed in Frenkel pair production during single-cascade simulations with a 5 keV PKA, overlapping cascade simulations revealed that Inconel 617-S tends to form fewer large interstitial clusters compared to $\text{Ni}_{59.8}\text{Cr}_{27.1}\text{Co}_{13.1}$, resulting in lower dislocation densities at higher doses. This suggests that the presence of 9.7 % Mo in Inconel 617-S may play a key role in influencing long-term defect accumulation behavior.
2. Tensile simulations demonstrated that irradiation-induced defects impact the mechanical properties of both alloys. In both compositions, irradiation led to a decrease in yield strength (YS), with $\text{Ni}_{59.8}\text{Cr}_{27.1}\text{Co}_{13.1}$ exhibiting a greater reduction in YS compared to Inconel 617-S.
3. Irradiation led to a modest reduction in Young's modulus in both alloys, consistent with the accumulation of dislocation networks that introduce an anelastic response. The softening effect was more evident at higher dislocation densities and supports the view that even early-stage irradiation can influence the elastic behavior of complex alloys.
4. In Inconel 617-S, the defect concentration (~ 0.004) is comparable to literature-reported values for equimolar NiCrCo, a medium-entropy alloy with better radiation resistance than Ni, NiCo, NiFe, and NiFeCo. However, Inconel 617-S may exhibit even greater radiation resistance than equimolar NiCrCo, as it forms fewer dislocations and smaller interstitial clusters under irradiation up to 0.2 dpa.

In summary, this study suggests that the addition of 9.7 % Mo in Inconel 617-S helps suppress irradiation-induced defect accumulation, thereby enhancing radiation resistance at the atomic scale. These findings offer valuable atomistic insights into the irradiation response of complex alloys and may support future efforts in the design of radiation-tolerant materials for nuclear applications. Further investigations should explore the temperature dependence of defect evolution and the long-term stability of irradiation-induced dislocations to better understand alloy performance under extreme conditions.

Fig. 11. (a, c) Distribution of atomic species in interstitials formed during overlapping cascade simulations at various doses (cascade numbers) for Inconel 617-S and Ni_{59.8}Cr_{27.1}Co_{13.1} (b, d) Distribution of atomic species in primary knock-on atoms (PKAs) selected during overlapping cascade simulations at various doses for Inconel 617-S and Ni_{59.8}Cr_{27.1}Co_{13.1}. The guidelines indicate the atomic percentage of each element in Inconel 617-S and Ni_{59.8}Cr_{27.1}Co_{13.1}.

Fig. 12. (a) Dislocation density vs. strain in irradiated (155 cascades) and unirradiated Inconel 617-S under [010] loading. Snapshots of dislocation nucleation during tensile loading in (b) unirradiated and (c) irradiated (155 cascades) Inconel 617-S.

Table 3

Elastic constants and Young's modulus values (theoretical and simulation-based), in GPa, for unirradiated Inconel 617-S and Ni_{59.8}Cr_{27.1}Co_{13.1} along the [001] crystallographic direction.

	C ₁₁	C ₁₂	Theoretical E _[001]	Fitted E _[001]
Inconel 617-S	252.25	165.36	121.30	124.24 ± 0.13
Ni _{59.8} Cr _{27.1} Co _{13.1}	238.05	149.74	122.45	123.16 ± 0.10

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Amin Esfandiarpour: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Tomasz Stasiak:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Zbigniew Kozioł:** Writing – review & editing,

Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software. **Jarosław Jasiński:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Funding acquisition, Data curation. **Łukasz Kurpaska:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Conceptualization. **Mikko Alava:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary materials

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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